

RE-DWELL Summer School 3 (Reading)

Deliverable 3.6

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RE-DWELL

Deliverable 3.6 RE-DWELL Summer School 3 (Reading)

Version 1

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Executive summary

Three, five-day international summer schools have been planned to take place in [Nicosia](#) (November 2021), [Valencia](#) (July 2022) and [Reading](#) (July 2023) as part of the RE-DWELL project. The last of these summer schools, organized by the University of Reading (UREAD), has been carried out in Reading, from July 3- 7th, 2023. This report focuses on the results of this summer school.

The theme of the summer school, “Innovations in Affordable and Sustainable Housing,” was thus addressed from multiple perspectives through presentations from invited speakers from professional practice, and academia.

The [programme](#) of activities of the Reading summer school aimed at fostering the exchange of knowledge across early-stage researchers (ESRs), supervisors and non-academic organisations, on addressing the challenges and opportunities of the design process in meeting needs for affordable and sustainable housing. It is noteworthy that this meeting has a strong presence of partner organisations, with five participating in the event—two from the UK and three from other countries.

The programme included workshops to support the development of ESR’s research through training activities related to two ongoing structured courses: RMT3 “Transferring research findings to community stakeholders” and TS3 “Communication and dissemination; Engagement and impact”. Following the blended-learning approach the activities of the courses began online, to be continued in-person during the event.

In addition to the activities at the University of Reading, there were lectures held in London at the premises of Clarion Housing Association, a partner organisation, and at Pollard Thomas Edwards architectural office, a firm conducting research on affordable housing. Additionally, there was a site visit to a new “build-to-rent” housing development in Reading town centre.

This summer school placed particular emphasis on sessions related to WP4, “Transdisciplinary Affordable and Sustainable Housing Research Framework.” The goal of work in this package is to integrate the research projects of ESRs within a transdisciplinary framework, which is being developed bottom-up and top-down. A serious game session facilitated discussions on the foundation of this framework, laying the groundwork for its further development. Additionally, participants discussed a shared strategy for collecting inputs from ESRs’ projects to create a cohesive set of reports.

Before the summer school, a series of meetings were held to discuss this with the ESRs and gather feedback in preparation for the event. The feedback received from them after the [Valencia summer school](#) was to include an introduction to the local context and ensure representation from a diverse range of disciplines, including social, economic, and architectural fields, to inform their research. Accordingly, invited speakers came from a range of disciplines to inform the debate. Other feedback from ESRs from previous events included a request for more interactive sessions, more time for discussion and also guidance on tasks to be conducted during the summer school.

The summer school was evaluated by participants through an online survey (Annex 1), with the overall results discussed in Section 2.2.

1. Introduction

This report summarizes the work done during the [third RE-DWELL summer school](#) held in Reading, from July 3 to 7, 2023, organized by the University of Reading (UREAD). It encompasses the activities done by early-stage researchers (ESRs) prior to the workshop, the sessions facilitated by the tutors of on-going courses, the sessions dedicated to the development of the RE-DWELL research framework, onsite and online lectures and site visits, outputs of the workshop, and the evaluation of the programme by ESRs and supervisors/co-supervisors.

The programme of the Reading summer school aimed at fostering the exchange of knowledge across ESRs, supervisors and non-academic organisations, on the challenges and opportunities of the design process in realizing needs for affordable and sustainable housing. The activities were planned to enable a follow-up on the development of ESR's research through training activities related to the ongoing structured courses (two sessions on "RMT3 Research, Methods and Tools" and "TS 3 Transferrable Skills") and through networking activities between the individual projects, supervisors/co-supervisors and partner organisations.

The summer school addressed the theme of "Innovations in Affordable and Sustainable Housing" through a programme encompassing five sub-themes which are part of the RE-DWELL training structure:

- **Design of affordable and sustainable housing** – challenges and opportunities that affordable and sustainable housing planning and design poses for architects and planners, developers and inhabitants; collaborative housing, co-production, social innovation, and social experimentation in housing and neighbourhoods; understanding the building/community relationships and opportunities.
- **Transdisciplinarity research for affordable and sustainable housing** – appropriate theoretical grounding of the ESRs' research projects in a transdisciplinary manner; analysis and position of own research and that of another ESR within the field of housing studies in relation to different disciplines; analysis of diverse research approaches to housing in terms of research aims, theoretical backgrounds and methods
- **Social housing design** – factors involved in the design of social housing; financial models and incentives; community resilience through community planning for housing development; encouraging participation, and enabling cogeneration of housing schemes.
- **Ethics in research on sustainable and affordable housing** – challenges and opportunities of conducting research; ethics, open science and intellectual property rights; ethics, principles and sustainability; ethical processes and challenges associated with engaging with participants and data management.
- **Sustainable planning and design for affordable housing in listed neighbourhoods** – challenges in neighbourhood regeneration projects; retrofitting; adaptively reusing building stock at the scale of the building and the scale of the neighbourhood; environmental and bioclimatic design; learning from the past, applying to today's challenges; and social sustainability in a time of population shifts.

Invited speakers from professional practice, academia, local partner organisations and experts from the host University addressed topics related to the summer school's theme.

The invited speakers addressed the subject of innovative and sustainable housing from their academic and professional perspective. Each lecture session included debate and group discussions. There were lectures taking place in London, at the premises of Clarion Housing Association, a partner organisation who are offering secondments to several students, and at Pollard Thomas Edwards architectural office, a firm that has undertaken their own research around affordable housing. In addition, there was a site visit to a local housing development in Reading town centre a new "build-to-rent" scheme.

Some preparatory work for the summer school was undertaken collaboratively with ESRs. This involved holding meetings with the coordinators of RMT3 and TS3 courses, focusing on preparing sessions for the summer school and addressing assignments in advance for discussion during the event.

To ensure alignment with the research development of ESRs, the programme was discussed in advance with them, ensuring that the planned sessions could effectively support their ongoing research. There were sessions dedicated to discussing deliverables for the REDWELL project, providing a focused opportunity to address and explore project milestones.

1.1. Contribution of local partners

The University of Reading (UREAD) had the responsibility of organising the summer school. There were a set of invited speakers and experts from across a range of disciplines who brought their experience to the discussion around innovations of affordable and sustainable housing.

The local expertise at the University of Reading includes some researchers with backgrounds in housing policy and planning to inform the debate and discussion.

There are some associated research projects at the University of Reading concerned with aspects of community consultation and some of the researchers presented at the summer school. In addition there are a set of Knowledge Transfer Partnerships (KTP funded by UKRI a government funded scheme) on the theme of social value . These are partnerships with industry to deliver innovation and research. One of the speakers brought her experience of post-occupancy evaluation to the summer school to inform ideas of how this could be an effective tool for housing.

1.2. Participants

There were thirty-one participants (one of them on-line), eleven supervisors/co-supervisors, one communication manager and six partner organisations' representatives (Table 1) and thirteen ESRs (Table 2). They engaged in activities and exchanged knowledge on the challenges and opportunities of the design process in realizing needs for affordable and sustainable housing.

Table 1. Participants from beneficiaries and partner organisations

	Beneficiary / Partner organisation	Member	Presence
1.	B1 FUNITEC (La Salle-URL), Spain, Project Coordinator	Leandro Madrazo	In-person
2.	B2 Université Grenoble-Alps	Adriana Diaconu	In-person
3.	B3 University of Sheffield, United Kingdom	Karim Hadjri	In-person
4.	B4 University of Zagreb, Croatia	Gojko Bezovan	In-person
5.	B5 Hungarian Academy of Sciences Centre of Excellence, Hungary	Adrienne Csizmady	In-person
6.	B6 University of Cyprus, Cyprus	Nadia Charalambous	In-person
7.	B7 Universitat Politècnica de València, Spain	Carla Sentieri	In-person
8.	B8 TU Delft, Netherlands	Marja Elsinga	In-person
9.	B8 TU Delft, Netherlands	Gerard van Bortel	In-person
10.	B9 ISCTE- Instituto Universitário de Lisboa, Portugal	Alexandra Paio	In-person
11.	B9 ISCTE- Instituto Universitário de Lisboa, Portugal	Mafalda Casais (communication manager)	In-person
12.	B10 UREAD- University of Reading	Lorraine Farrelly	In-person
13.	PO1-Lisbon City Council	Margarida Maurício	In-person
14.	PO1-Lisbon City Council	Maria Antónia Victoria	In-person
15.	PO6 - Clarion Housing Group	Elanor Warwick	In-person
16.	PO8 - Cyprus Land Development Corporation	Charalambos Iacovou	In-person
17.	PO9 - South Yorkshire Housing Association	Natalie Newman	On-line
18.	PO11 - Housing Europe	Margarida Maurício	In-person

Table 2. Participating early-stage researchers

ESR #	ESR name	Presence
1.	Annette Davis	In-person
2.	Saskia Furman	In-person
4.	Aya Elghandour	In-person
5.	Mahmoud Alsaeed	In-person
6.	Marko Horvat	In-person
7.	Anna Martin	In-person
8.	Andreas Panagidis	In-person
9.	Effrosyni Roussou	In-person
10.	Zoe Tzika	In-person
11.	Tijn Croon	In-person
13.	Androniki Pappa	In-person
14.	Carolina Martin	In-person
15.	Leonardo Ricaurte	In-person

1.3. RTM and TS training activities

A follow-up on the development of ESR's research was facilitated through training activities related to the on-going structured courses: "RMT3 Research, Methods and Tools" (Figure 1) and "TS3 Transferrable Skills" (Figure 2).

Research Methods and Tools 3 (RMT3)

Figure 1. RMT3 course structure as integrated with the network activities

Transferable Skills 3 (TS3)

Figure 2. TS3 course structure as integrated with the network activities

1.4. Dissemination

Dissemination aiming at reaching and positively influencing relevant stakeholders and end users through their direct or indirect engagement with the summer school's activities and outcomes, was performed before, during and after the event. The dissemination activities aimed at informing researchers, local associations, professors, PhD students, policy makers and the general public about the aims, activities and the outcomes of the Reading summer school.

The summer school [programme](#) was available in the RE-DWELL website before the meeting (Figures 3, 4).

Figures 3, 4. Summer school programme

During the summer school, the daily activities were reported on [Twitter](#) (Figure 5) and [LinkedIn](#) (Figure 6). The participation of the communication manager in the meeting contributed to provide a daily account of the activities published on the various social media channels.

Figure 5. Post in Twitter

Figure 6. Post in LinkedIn

At the end of the summer school, a reel with highlights was published in [LinkedIn](#), [Instagram](#) (Figure 7), [Facebook](#) and [Twitter](#).

Figure 7. Reel published in Instagram

In addition, three ESRs published their reflections on the summer school presentations and discussion in the network blog (Figure 8):

- [“The ‘regeneration wave,’ hopefully not another missed opportunity to create social value,”](#) by Leonardo Ricaurte

- [“Retrofit and Social Engagement | We can do better,”](#) by Saskia Furman

- [“Serious Games in Housing Research,”](#) by Mahmoud Alseid

Figure 8. Blogposts by ESRs after the summer school

2. Programme

The summer school was carried out at the London Road Campus School of Architecture , University of Reading from Monday 3rd July – Friday 7th July. It was an in-person event, with facilities for online for those who could not attend.

The programme was divided in daily sessions/themes in an attempt to link the training and research activities taking place within RE-DWELL with relevant expertise of external stakeholders from professional practice, academia and local actors, and site visits (Table 3).

Table 3. Programme of the Reading Summer School

Day	Timetable	Activities
DAY 1 Monday, 3 July, 2023	10:00 to 10:30	Welcome
	10:15 to 12:00	Knowledge and evidence-based housing: Creating impact in housing research
	12:00- 13:00	TS3 workshop: developing an impact plan
	13:00 to 14:00	Lunch
	14:00 to 15:00	Tools and Methods of POE
	15.30 to 17:00	Workshop reflection on assignments
DAY 2 Tuesday, 4 July, 2023	19:00	Dinner
	10:00 to 11:00	Innovation in finance models for affordable housing: CLTs and Co-housing
	11:00 to 12:00	Innovation in Housing Design
	12:00 to 13:00	Discussion New models affordable housing
	13:00 to 14:00	Lunch Break
	14:00 to 16:00	RMT 3 course: Exploring gaps and challenges in the transfer of research results
	16:00 to 17:00	WP4 : Deliverables 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3
	19:00	Dinner
DAY 3 Wednesday, 5 July, 2023	10:00 to 11:00	Innovation in housing research - What next?
	11:00 to 12:00	REDWELL framework
	12:00- 13:00	Game session
	13:00 to 14:00	Lunch break
	14:00 to 17:00	Game session continuation
	18:00 to 19:00	Station Hill development site visit
	19:30	Dinner

DAY 4 Thursday, 6 July, 2023	10:00 to 13:00	Clarion Housing Association, London
	13:00 to 14:00	Lunch break
	14:30 to 17:00	Pollard Thomas Edwards architects, London
	18:00	Dinner
DAY 5 Friday, 7 July, 2023	09:00 to 09:15	WP4 discussions and outputs
	09:15 to 10:45	D4.1 design planning and building
	10:45 to 11:00	Break
	11:00 to 12:30	D4.2 community participation
	12:30 to 13:30	Lunch
	13:30 to 15:00	D4.3 Policy and Finance
	15:00 to 15:30	Wrap up and conclusions

noted the challenges inherent in each domain due to their distinct temporal focuses (science/past, policy/future, media/present), varied languages, and diverse audiences.

One key issue Foe pointed out is the complexity of scientific information for policymakers, leading to a struggle in implementing scientifically grounded policies. On the other hand, policies that gain popularity often overlook or dismiss research findings. Think tanks play a crucial role in managing these tensions and facilitating effective communication across these domains.

Philip Graham identified five key factors influencing housing affordability: supply, tax system, interest rates, borrowing capacity, and income levels. He asserted that addressing only the supply aspect will not fully resolve the housing affordability issue. In the UK, around 65% of dwellings are owner-occupied, while 35% are rented. Government policies aim to increase homeownership, benefiting the state through tax revenue and boosting credit activity in the financial system.

Graham pointed out the challenge of cramped living conditions in the UK, with many residing in small homes until they can afford larger ones. However, climbing the housing ladder incurs additional taxes, hindering upward mobility. He raised questions about how individuals can move up the housing ladder without facing excessive costs and how to encourage downsizing as people age. One potential solution is adjustable housing—dwellings that can be expanded or reduced in size over time (Figure 12). However, Graham noted that existing tax systems, planning regulations, and mortgages are not currently equipped to support this concept.

Figure 12. Adjustable housing dimensions, by Phil Graham

Flora Samuel, discussed knowledge transfer in architectural research and practice, emphasizing key issues like climate change, inclusion, and well-being. She identified several obstacles to effective knowledge transfer, including its time-consuming nature, long-term impact, and differences in rigour and pace between academia and practice.

Samuel highlighted a disparity between academic and practice research: academic researchers are often measured by publication metrics, while practice research is less frequently documented. This poses a challenge, as practitioners may not engage with academic

publications. One crucial aspect is the role of architectural education in bridging this gap. Architects need training in essential research skills, including academic writing and reading scholarly journals. However, the design studio is still considered a fundamental research method for architects. Lastly, Samuel advocated for the reintroduction of practitioners into educational settings to enhance the connection between academia and practice in the field of architecture.

The presentations were followed by a panel discussion with the three speakers (Figure 13), and involving ESRs, partners and supervisors .

Figure 13. A moment in the discussion of Flora Samuel, Phil Graham and Chris Foe

Two main inquiries arose during the discussion. Firstly, there is a question about whether demand is the primary driver of housing unaffordability. Secondly, there is a consideration of the democratic implications when policymakers follow advice from researchers.

Additional issues addressed were the need to transform social value into interest rates, with ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) being suggested as a potential avenue. The conversation also touched upon the growing disconnection between research and policy, and the varying levels of recognition and respect for experts in different countries. An urgent call, particularly in the UK, is made to rebuild knowledge in the public sector to restore trust.

TS3 workshop: developing an impact plan

After the presentations in the previous session about creating impact from research, there was a session when the ESRs could talk informally around their own impact plans and how they were developing this in response to the TS3 task on impact planning. The three speakers were available for informal feedback on this task (Figure 14).

Figure 14. Workshop session

Tools and methods of POE

The speaker and topic in this afternoon session was:

- Dr Gloria Vargas, Research Associate in a partnership between Pollard Thomas Edwards Architects (Figure 15) - *Post Occupancy Evaluation (POE)*

Vargas shared her experience with post-occupancy evaluation (POE), which began with her PhD on short-term thermal history in transitional lobby spaces, completed at the University of Sheffield in 2014. Originally focused on assessing how well a building is functioning, POE has evolved to encompass social value, emotions, people's perceptions, and experiences. She highlighted the expanded scope of POE, noting its potential to assist architects in offering improved services to clients, addressing performance gaps at both the building and social levels, and providing evidence-based data. Key challenges include incorporating user feedback into the design process and ensuring that lessons learned are effectively applied by residents. Currently, POE is emerging as a valuable tool for enhancing architectural design and building performance through a holistic understanding of user experiences.

Figure 15. Presentation by Gloria Vargas

Workshop: reflection on assignments

The workshop was a component of the TS3 course, where ESRs were tasked with recognizing the significance of dissemination to key stakeholders, identifying and mapping target audiences, and exploring effective communication methods. Reflections from the secondments were used to create a plan for communication and engagement. ESRs presented their draft ideas for the TS3 tasks. There was a discussion and feedback on each presentation (Figures 16, 17) to support ESRs with the completion of the task and share ideas for research communication and impact of their research.

SOCIAL VALUE

In the context of the built environment, social value is created when buildings, places and infrastructure support environmental, economic and social well-being, thereby improving people's quality of life.

UK Green Building Council. (2021). Framework for Defining Social Value. <https://www.ukgbc.org/ukgbc-work/framework-for-defining-social-value/>

Social sustainability

4

LIMITLESS POTENTIAL | LIMITLESS OPPORTUNITIES | LIMITLESS IMPACT

Figure 16. Presentation by Leonardo Ricaurte

Beneficiaries

Who owns the problem?

Building owners planning retrofit of their buildings for their tenants (often resulting in performance gaps)

National Government responsible for green transition and population wellbeing

Who experiences the problem?

Residents living in the building

Retrofit designers without an informed brief central to the needs of the end user

Contractors at odds with residents

Building owners coming up against conflict and rejection of retrofit

Who is influential and lobbies for change?

National Government can write engagement obligations into policy

Building owners to lobby government to support engagement (e.g. funding)

Architects and retrofit designers can lobby building owners to see the value in tenant engagement

Residents right of retrofit refusal

Tenants Associations have a "voice at the table" and can lobby building owners.

Figure 17. Presentation by Saskia Furman

DAY 2

Tuesday, 4 July

The morning session was dedicated to two presentations by key speakers followed by a debate. Lorraine Farrelly moderated the session.

The speakers and topics were:

- Prof Kath Scanlon, London School of Economics (Figure 18) – *Innovation in finance models for affordable housing: CLTs and Co-housing*
- Meredith Bowles, Director Mole Architects – *Innovation in housing design*

Kath Scanlon emphasized the need for creative approaches to achieve affordable housing, listing options such as collaborative housing on public land, private sector involvement, Community Land Trusts (CLTs), modular housing, and direct provision by public authorities. The presentation underscored the complexity of achieving affordable housing and the need for a multifaceted, context-specific approach to address the various challenges in different regions.

The key points addressed were the following:

- **Cohousing Benefits:** Cohousing can reduce costs by incorporating shared spaces and reducing unit sizes. Inclusionary zoning ensures a percentage of private developments is allocated to social housing, though negotiations with developers may be time-consuming.
- **Financial Tools:** Tax breaks, such as the Low-Income Housing Tax Credit in the USA, are valuable for supporting affordable housing. Additionally, modular housing was highlighted for its cost reduction and faster delivery but requires a continuous order chain from factories. Kath suggested that a combination of financial tools is typically necessary for achieving affordability.
- **Global Examples:** Vienna and Singapore are recognized for successful housing affordability models. However, their experiences cannot be easily transposed to other countries, it is necessary to adapt the strategies to specific contexts, considering historical, political, legal, and cultural factors, as well as land ownership practices.

Figure 18. Presentation by Kath Scanlon

Meredith Bowles presented [Marmalade Lane](#) (Figure 19), a co-housing scheme built in Cambridge in 2018. The architects developed a brief after consulting with community members and initiated a competition for developers. The resulting design featured street-based architecture, respecting traditional housing, with family houses and apartments surrounding a central open space. While owners had the option to choose colours and materials, planning regulations limited these choices.

Figure 19. Marmalade Lane cohousing community, Cambridge

Cohousing, as Bowles described it, is not just about providing physical space but also about building intentional communities and relationships. Social interactions are crucial, requiring time and commitment from all involved, also from architects. Several barriers to cohousing projects

were identified, including high land prices, affordability issues, funding challenges, and a lack of available sites. Overcoming these obstacles may imply changes in government and local regulations.

Bowles highlighted the significant obstacle of land cost to housing affordability. He referred to the speculative nature of land value and called for innovative policies to ensure fair access to land for housing purposes. The message underscored the importance of addressing systemic issues to promote equitable housing solutions.

After the presentations Scanlon and Bowles engaged in a discussion with RE-DWELL members (Figure 20), highlighting the potential role of housing associations in providing affordable housing, despite resident scepticism. They emphasized the importance of fostering social cohesion in cohousing developments, particularly by ensuring acceptance of new residents. The conversation extended to exploring how successful community-building experiences can be applied to diverse situations, including retrofitting. A question was raised regarding whether affordability is a universal problem or one that can only be effectively addressed at the local level.

The discussion also delved into the issue of taxes, noting their typically national focus rather than city-level jurisdiction. While cities have an obligation to provide affordable housing, economic constraints outside their decision-making capacities may limit their capacity, with land being identified as a valuable asset.

The limitations of community land trusts (CLTs) for social housing were acknowledged, as they appear to work more effectively for middle-income groups. The market's inadequacy in providing housing for everyone was recognized, emphasizing the crucial role of financing in developing solutions for affordable housing.

Figure 20. A moment in the conversation with Kath Scanlon and Meredith Bowles

RMT3 course: Exploring gaps and challenges in the transfer of research results

This workshop, which is part of the RMT3 course "Transferring research findings to community", facilitated by Adrienne Csizmady from CSS (Figure 21), served as a collaborative and preparatory session for ESRs.

Figure 21. Introduction to the workshop, by Adrienne Csizmady

Prior to their arrival at Reading, ESRs had already prepared their presentations (Figures 22, 23).

Figure 22. Links between data collection methods and non-academic audiences, by Mahmoud Alseed, Marko Horvat and Leonardo Ricaurte

	Presentation method	Challenges/Obstacles
Andreas		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interpreting personal beliefs and presenting them as scientific data Language To explain the significance of new knowledge/novel concepts and explaining the opportunities of changing established norms
Phryne	(indirect) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> social media local press website poster pin-up in the neighbourhood 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public distrust of institutions Maintaining momentum, engagement and interest
Androniki	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interactive dashboard Research report Presentation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Language Raising awareness on the importance of translating qualitative information into strategies

Figure 23. Links between data collection methods and non-academic audiences, by Andreas Panagidis, Androniki Pappa and Phryne Roussou

The primary objective of the activity was to identify gaps and challenges in collaboration with external organisations, placing specific emphasis on the methods employed to gather information for secondments or PhD theses. The discussions were taking place during the teams' presentations (Figure 24).

Figure 24. Presentation by Tijn Croon, Carolina Martín and Saskia Furman

In teams (Figures 25, 26), ESRs engaged in discussions on comparative research methodologies, considering their personal preferences and focusing on the three RE-DWELL research areas. Throughout the session, they delved into methods for engaging with local decision-makers and civil society organisations. They explored challenges associated with transferring research findings, considering disciplinary differences, and recognizing national disparities in the use of dissemination methods. Participants identified and discussed the most effective ways to communicate their research results to target audiences. Overall, the

workshop provided a platform for collaborative exploration and strategizing to enhance the impact of the ESRs' research in their respective fields.

Figures 25, 26. Team discussions during the workshop. Left: Anna Martin, Zoe Tzika and Annette Davis; right, Androniki Pappa, Phryne Roussou, Andreas Panagidis

WP4 : Deliverables 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3

The session, led by Marja Elsinga from TUD, leader of WP 4 "Transdisciplinary affordable and sustainable housing research framework," was dedicated to discussing the contributions of ESRs to Deliverables 4.1, 4.2, and 4.3, each one focusing on exploring each of three research areas of the project (Design, planning and building; Community participation; and Policy and financing) from a transdisciplinary perspective.

The group was divided into three (Figures 27, 28, 29), each led by the supervisor responsible of the respective deliverable—Nadia Charalambous (UCY), Adrienne Csizmady (CSS), and Gojko Bezovan (UNIZG). Following the discussion, a shared structure was agreed upon to compile the inputs of researchers for the ongoing reports.

Figure 27. Focus group "Design, planning and building"

Figure 28. Focus group "Community participation"

Figure 29. Focus group "Policy and financing"

DAY 3

Wednesday, 5 July

Innovation in housing research: What next?

The session was facilitated by Lorraine Farrelly. The speakers and topics were:

- Roland Karthaus, architect, from Matter Architecture (Figure 20) – *Housing research and design: The case of intergenerational housing*
- Ruchit Purohit, researcher, University of Cambridge (Figure 31) – *Social innovation in housing and research: Mapping and data*

Figure 30. Online presentation by Roland Karthaus, Matter Architecture

Figure 31. Presentation by Ruchit Purohit

Karthaus delivered his presentation online. He presented two grant-funded projects: prison design and intergenerational housing. Both explore the interaction between people and their environment, studying how built spaces and lived spaces connect.

Traditional prisons are separated from the outside world. The “Wellbeing in Prison Design” (Figure 32) guidelines created by Matter Architecture challenges those limits. Integrating convicts with their surroundings and training them in construction skills promotes their rehabilitation and reduces re-entry rates. They can participate in renovating neighbourhood buildings, fostering community engagement and skills development. Reinventing the prison environment has both social and economic benefits.

Cells

Typical situation

- The typical cell contains most of the elements required for daily activities, but the layout does not enable maximum flexibility nor use of the space. Many typical exercises that people might do in their own space are not possible in a typical cell, such as press-ups
- There is inadequate storage, particularly for clothing and the height of the cell is not made use of due to anti-ligature requirements
- Lighting is not dimmable and limited personalisation of the space is possible

1.1.2 People factors / Physical / Fitness

Wellbeing in prison design: Design guide

100

Possible design response

- A more intensive design process and design review incorporating product and furniture design expertise should be undertaken to make the cell as habitable, personalisable and adaptable as possible, whilst continuing to ensure safety and security
- Overall cell dimensions should be reviewed

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matter

Figure 32 . "Wellbeing in Prison Design", by Matter Architecture

The second work focuses on intergenerational housing. Karthaus asked: "Why we do segregate people by age when we design housing." There is evidence that living in inadequate dwellings has consequences on the well-being of older people. Shared spaces favour the conviviality among people from different ages. Gardening helps to delimit a personal territory, and at the same time facilitates dialogue and mutual support.

Housing schemes can be classified by the age of the residents. Mainstream homes (young single, families), specialized homes (ageing with home support) and care homes. With intergenerational housing we can avoid, or delay, the care homes. However, mixed-used buildings do not necessarily mix people. To combine a school with an elderly home does not mean that pupils and seniors will meet.

Social benefits, management and design are interrelated. The key are the social benefits: we want to design houses for people's well-being. But providing spaces is not enough, even well-designed spaces. It is necessary to foster connections between people. Social management comes into play.

Purohit presented CCQL – Community Consultation for Quality of Life, a UKRI-funded project conducted by Reading, Cardiff, Edinburgh, and Ulster universities. The project aims to involve citizens in decision-making processes related to their wellbeing in cities, enabling active participation in planning decisions. To facilitate this, an environment was developed, incorporating an urban room, a GIS tool, and the quality-of-life framework

Pilot cases were implemented in four cities across the UK through the use of urban rooms located in neutral contexts (Figure 33), serving as communal areas that people can claim as their own to avoid undesired affiliations with any private or public entity.

Several open issues for future development were identified during the research project. One of them is the need to consolidate the tested environments, requiring support from local administrations. Additionally, there is a potential avenue for analysing feedback from participants in urban rooms and digital maps to derive actionable insights.

Figure 33. Urban room of the CCQL project

RE-DWELL framework

In the period between the Zagreb workshop held from March 28th to 31st 2023, and the Reading summer school, on-going work was conducted through distant meetings along parallel lines (Figure 34). These meetings involved ESRs, supervisors and partner organisations. The aim was to align and progress along these lines of work in parallel, enabling all network members to contribute. A survey was conducted during a supervisory board meeting held online on May 22, 2023. It included questions formulated by ESRs to partner organisations about the challenges they faced in their daily practice related to affordable and sustainable housing developments. The collected answers were used in the serious game session played in Reading, and further discussed with the participants.

Figure 34. From Zagreb workshop to Reading summer school: parallel lines of work

The session continued from the previous day regarding Deliverables 4.1, 4.2, and 4.3. Each supervisor responsible for a deliverable presented the work carried out by the team of ESRs working on it (Figures 35, 36, 37). The presentations facilitated an understanding of the various approaches adopted for each of the three research areas and highlighted the diversity of styles employed by ESRs in conducting literature research. It also revealed the need to define a shared structure to continue with the collective work.

Figures 35, 36, 37. Presentation of the on-going work in Deliverables 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3, by Nadia Charalambous, Adrienne Csizmady and Gojko Bezovan

Game session: Building together RE-DWELL affordable and sustainable housing framework

The objective of this interactive session, facilitated by Alexandra Paio (Figure 38) from ISCTE, was to engage participants in a serious game on the affordability and sustainability of housing.

Figure 38. Start of the game session

The game was played with three kinds of cards (Figures 39, 40):

- **Research Questions** cards (orange), with contents derived from ESRs' research project
- **Practice-based cards** (green), included methods, tools and actors involved in the provision of affordable and sustainable housing, and were derived from the vocabulary and case study library
- **Policies, Projects, Partnerships** cards (blue) contained the insights provided by RE-DWELL partner organisations in survey previously conducted with them

Re-DWELL Transdisciplinary Game Instructions

Overview & Aim

Re-Dwell Transdisciplinary game collects the knowledge produced by the Re-Dwell network in the topic of Affordable and Sustainable Housing. The game invites players to collaboratively create scenarios in response to certain issues.

Contents

The game includes three types of cards:

<p>x22</p>		
<p>The Research Questions Cards contain questions that relate to affordable and sustainable housing (defined by the ESRI research projects)</p>	<p>The Practice-based Approach Cards include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - methods - tools - actors <p>(No tool based on ESRI RE-DWELL Vocabulary and Case-Studies)</p>	<p>The Policies, Projects, Partnerships Cards (defined based on the Survey of partner organizations and Re-Dwell Dialogues (online))</p>

Re-Dwell Game will be played in two rounds of 1 hour each, following the instruction given in the next page.

The game will be played in 5 groups, each consisted of ESRs, Partner organizations and supervisors/co-supervisors.

Reading Summer School

Steps

-

1 In your group, look at the **Research Questions** cards and select one that is of common interest. This will be your topic throughout the 1st round of the game. Place it in the center of the table.
Tip: If the group cannot reach an agreement, let luck decide for you.
-

2 Equally share the **Practice-Based Approach** cards and the **Policies, Projects, Partnerships** cards among the players.
-

3 Take 5 minutes to look into your **Practice-Based Approach** cards and select the ones that you find relevant to the question, placing them in front of you.
Tip: You can use the blank cards to propose your own responses.
-

4 In rotation, present your selected **Practice-Based Approach** cards to the rest of the group and justify your responses.

After everyone's presentation, discuss and collectively decide on the cards that better respond to the question. There is no limit in the number of cards to be used. Place the agreed **Practice-Based Approach** cards next to the **Research Questions** card.
Tip: You can organise your selected cards into groups to start creating clusters on the board.
-

5 Repeat the steps 3-5, this time using the **Policies, Projects, Partnerships** cards.
Tips: You can attach the final Policies, Projects, Partnerships cards directly to the Research Question card, or the Practice-Based Approach cards.
-

6 Take a look at your final board, discuss and re-organise the cards to narrate your scenario.
-

7 Fill-in the online form and prepare a 5minute pitch.
<https://forms.office.com/e/wAb5JLjPR5>
Try a second round of the game, by starting with a Policies, Projects, Partnerships card.

Reading Summer School

Figures 39, 40. Game cards and guidelines

The group was divided into five teams, each focusing on one the three RE-DWELL research areas (Table 4). The teams were composed of ESRs, partner organisations and supervisors attending the meeting and other who were invited to follow online.

Table 4. Teams' composition

#	Research area focus	ESRs	Partner organisations	Supervisors
1.	Design, planning and building	Anna Martin, Aya Elghandour, Zoe Tzika	Elanor Warwick, Clarion Housing Group	Leandro Madrazo, Gerard van Bortel
2.	Design, planning and building	Andreas Panagidis, Annette Davis, Alex Fernández (online)	Charalambos Iacovou, Cyprus Land Development Corporation	Nadia Charalambous, Lorraine Farrelly
3.	Community participation	Androniki Pappa, Carolina Martin, Tijn Croon	Maria Antónia Victória, Lisbon City Council	Adrienne Csizmady, Karim Hadjri
4.	Policy and Financing	Saskia Furman, Phryne Roussou	Margherita Marinelli, Housing Europe; Natalie Newman (online), South Yorkshire Housing Association	Marja Elsinga, Adriana Diaconu
5.	Policy and Financing	Mahmoud Alsaeed, Marko Horvat, Leonardo Ricaurte	Margarida Mauricio (Lisbon City Council)	Gojko Bezovan, Carla Sentieri

Following the guidelines, participants first had to agree on the cards they would use and then discuss how to put them together. During this process, the knowledge each participant possessed, derived from their unique perspective, research, or practice, was verbalized. The potential connections between research questions; methods, tools, actors; and projects, policies, and partnerships were discussed (Figures 41-44).

Figures 41-44. Participants during the game session

Throughout the discussion, various arrangements of the cards were laid out on the table and photographed (Figure 45). At the end of the session, the team filled out an evaluation form (Figure 46) describing the selected cards and the reasons for their choices. To conclude the session, a representative from each team shared and explained the process and outcome with the whole group.

Figure 45. One the arrangements created by Team 1

Figure 46. Online evaluation form

The game was played twice, and the contents of the evaluation forms were later analysed by Gerard van Bortel, from TUD. Some of the conclusions were that the design of the cards was too sophisticated and their content difficult to read, it could not be played online, and the rules should be simplified.

Station Hill development site visit

At the end of the day, the group visited [Station Hill](#), a mixed-use development located near the railway station. It includes 1,300 new homes (studios, and 1, 2, and 3-bedroom apartments for rent), office spaces, and amenities for residents. It is primarily intended for mid-upper class workers commuting to London. The first occupants are expected to arrive in the summer of 2023.

Representatives of the firm introduced the development to the group (Figure 47) and then guided them through the construction site (Figures 48, 49). They explained the architectural project and the financing strategy of the investors.

Figure 47. Introduction to the project by representatives of the developer

Figure 48. Group visit to construction site

Figure 49. Visit to one of the model apartments

DAY 4

Thursday, 6 July

Clarion Housing Association, London

The morning session took place at the premises of [Clarion Housing Association](#), a RE-DWELL partner organisation, in London. Elanor Warwick (Figure 50) shared insights into the association's history, and Paul Quinn, Iwona Grala, and Imogen Barber walked us through Clarion's practical approach to building regeneration.

Clarion oversees 125,000 homes, providing housing for approximately 300,000 people. Their focus is on creating welcoming spaces, sustainable homes, and vibrant communities.

Renovating their diverse building stock, spanning from the 1920s to the present, poses challenges. Given the differences in urban contexts, construction techniques, and building types, finding universal solutions is not straightforward. Another hurdle is the shortage of professionals skilled in building retrofitting.

In terms of new developments, Clarion sticks to five key principles: social value, promoting healthy spaces, adaptability and resilience, eco-friendly practices, and considerations for energy and carbon. External architectural firms commissioned for housing projects must adhere to these guidelines.

The political landscape significantly shapes the work of housing associations. Government budget allocations for affordable housing play a crucial role in determining what can be achieved. Decades of underinvestment have eroded the social housing stock in the UK (and at many other EU countries).

Figure 50. Presentation at Clarion Housing by Elanor Warwick

Pollard Thomas Edwards architects

In the afternoon, the group visited [Pollard Thomas Edwards Architects](#), where Tom Dollard and Grecia Castillo presented the firm's comprehensive work on sustainable housing, encompassing research, design, and construction. Sustainability is a core focus in their housing projects (Figure 51). They prioritize staying updated on changing regulations and provide training for their staff. The firm has developed their own sustainability design codes, which they implement in their projects.

Actively committed enhance sustainable practices, the architects collaborate with researchers and conduct studies such as "[Building for 2050](#)," emphasizing the importance of designing low-carbon housing through thoughtful design rather than relying solely on technology.

Firm's designers employ various tools during the initial stages of design to assess building performance such as covering lighting, energy consumption, and comfort. This comprehensive approach helps them understand the overall performance of the building. Despite this, some clients prefer that the building performance aspects are verified by experts during the later stages of a project, which can sometimes lead to disagreements with earlier assessments made by the architects at the design phase.

Figure 51. Presentation by Tom Dollard at Pollard Thomas Edwards architectural office, London

DAY 5

Friday, 7 July

The last day of the summer school was dedicated to advance in the development of the RE-DWELL research framework.

In the morning session, ESRs presented their ongoing PhD thesis work, detailing connections to the research lines of their peers (Figures 52, 53, 54). The presentations highlighted the varied implementation of the transdisciplinary approach within the RE-DWELL project: some ESRs incorporated it directly into their projects, include the concept of framework, while others aimed to define the scope of their research, leaving room for potential connections across projects.

The parallel work done in RMT3 and TS3 courses was evident in the presentations. Some researchers addressed the challenge of transitioning from “research questions” to “challenges” that are relevant to practitioners in the provision of affordable and sustainable housing (Figures 52-54). The next step of the collaborative development of the RE-DWELL research framework’s involves identifying challenges across multiple fields and actors in affordable and sustainable housing provision.

Figure 52. Housing challenges related to the three sustainability dimensions, by Carolina Martín

Figure 53. Challenges in the design and construction of affordable and sustainable housing, by Mahmoud Asead

Figure 54. Transferring knowledge from research to practice, by Andorniki Pappa

The discussion continued in the afternoon (Figures 55, 56). Seated around a table, ESRs, supervisors and partner organisations representatives shared their experiences with the serious game, exchanged their interpretations of the “RE-DWELL research framework,” and envisioned the next steps to take in its development. The recorded discussion will inform the next steps in developing the RE-DWELL transdisciplinary framework.

Figure 55. Final discussion

Figure 56. Participants at the end of the final discussion

2.2. Evaluation

Participants evaluated the workshop online, through an anonymous questionnaire (see Annex 1). It was answered by eight ESRs, nine supervisors/co-supervisors, and one partner organisation.

All the sessions were generally well-considered. In general, the supervisors rated the sessions more highly than the ESRs, but the majority of the participants evaluated the summer school positively. Every respondent rated the overall organization either 4 or 5 out of 5, apart from one ESR rating it a 1 out of 5. This resulted in an overall average rating of 4.4 out of 5 (see Table 5).

Table 5. Summary of the evaluation

Questions	Answers	Supervisors/ Co- supervisors	ESRs	Average
How would you rate the organization of the summer school?	18	4.8	3.9	4,4
"Knowledge and evidence-based housing: Creating impact in housing research" session	13	4.5	4.7	4,6
"Tools and methods of POE" session	13	4.5	4.1	4,3
"Workshop - Reflect on Assignments" session	10	4.3	4.1	4,2
"Innovation in finance models for affordable housing: CLTs and Co-housing" session	15	4.5	4.1	4,3
"Innovation in housing design" session	16	4.6	4.4	4,5
"Discussion New models of affordable housing" session	14	4.5	4.3	4,4
"RMT3 course: Exploring gaps and challenges in the transfer of research results" session	12	4.4	3.9	4,1
"Work package 4" session	13	4.3	3.7	4,0
"Innovation in housing research: What next?" session	16	4.1	4.3	4,2
"RE-DWELL Assessment Framework" session	16	4.0	4.0	4,0
"Game session" session	18	4.6	4.0	4,3
"Station Hill Reading Development Site Tour" session	15	3.8	3.4	3,6
"Regeneration projects: a microcosm of social housing activity" session (Clarion Housing visit)	14	4.7	4.1	4,4
"Introduction to social value housing tool KTP (Knowledge Transfer Partnership)" session (PTE visit)	12	4.8	4.3	4,5
"WP4 discussion and outputs" session	13	4.2	3.7	3,9
"Wrap-up, conclusions and follow-up" session	13	4.5	4.4	4,5

An analysis of the comments linked to each activity will help build a more detailed picture of the summer school outcome. It should be noted that not all respondents attended every session, especially towards the beginning of the summer school. Further, only three of the 8 ESRs who responded provided consistent comments for most of the questions. Of the supervisors, six of the nine respondents provide consistent comments.

Day 1 consisted of three sessions. First, "Knowledge and evidence-based housing: Creating impact in housing research" was especially highly rated by the ESRs (4.7 average):

"Great group of presenters and very interesting topics that help us understand ways to create impact through sharing their personal experiences."

"I found very inspiring all the lectures in this session, specially the one by Phil Graham that presented his practice-based PhD, focused on a transdisciplinary framework for improving adjustability of housing during use."

"Fascinating content."

However, one supervisor noted:

"UK-centred. Could have highlighted broader cross-national examples."

Next, the "Tools and Methods of POE" session also drew positive ratings and comments:

"Very grateful that Dr Gloria Vargas shared all those insights on POE with practical and operational toolboxes. Her work is inspiring for the development of our own methodological approaches."

One supervisor suggested:

"POE and its applications are very relevant for research on housing, however the discussion focused mainly on technical aspects and measurement tools. It would have been interesting to open it up to different applications and adaptations of POE to more qualitative aspects of housing."

The final session on Day 1 was "Workshop - Reflect on Assignments". It was positively noted that:

"The session was very helpful and fun. Lisa and Lorraine were excellent facilitators, helping as frame our research through very targeted questions, keeping a very nice energy during the session despite the long day."

However, one ESR noted a lack of time:

"It was interesting to present our reflections on the RMT3 course, but due to the lack of time there was no possibility for comments on our work, which would have been very useful."

Day 2 included five sessions. First, the session "Innovation in finance models for affordable housing: CLTs and Co-housing", which was positively received by the ESRs:

"Kath Scanlon's lecture was very stimulating, as she went through several economic models to provide affordability in housing, highlighting what Phil also mentioned on Monday, that housing cost is inevitably tied to the land cost."

"Great presentation of Kath's methodology, very inspiring and insightful."

"The discussion on the financial aspects of CLTs and Co-housing was particularly enlightening."

However, one supervisor noted:

"I don't feel there was enough information about innovation in finance."

Next was the session "Innovation in housing design", which was among the highest rated of all the sessions and drew many positive comments (4.5 overall average):

"Meredith was a very good presenter and showed us nice examples of co-housing projects."

"Meredith's lecture was really inspiring for many reasons: working closely with a community, creating tailor-made homes, using timber frame construction. This innovative process promoted by Mole architects touched upon many of the concepts I am researching on my thesis and brought to the table a real case in which standardisation, participation, environmental sustainability and variability of choice can coexist. It was as well interesting to see his post-evaluation of the process and how he would improve some of the methods in the next development."

"This human-centered approach to design was truly inspiring."

Next was the "Discussion New models of affordable housing", which drew less detailed but positive comments:

"It was an excellent idea to leave time for discussion after the morning session presentations. This organic way of discussion always ends up being very engaging."

"Very well done."

Then came the session "RMT3 course: Exploring gaps and challenges in the transfer of research results", where the group work was positively commented on by several ESRs:

"Thank you for leaving time to work in groups and share reflections among us during the summer school. We always learn so much from these exchanges and we also very much appreciate saving some workload in preparation of the summer school."

"I enjoyed seeing the different communication methods and tools the different PhD students have been using. When preparing the assignment with my team, the discussion was very rich and we learned from each other's processes and barriers..."

Though the same comment also went on to note time constraints, a running theme among several of the sessions:

"...But when presenting to the rest, as the time was limited, there was no possibility to discuss or suggest improvements to each of us."

The last Day 2 session was "Work package 4". This was rated lower by the ESRs, with an average of 3.7 among that group, though it still drew positive reflections from several ESRs:

"This was actually a very engaging discussion in groups. Discussing with peers of similar research interests we learn about challenges, methodologies, definitions and exchange advice. I think it would have been even more valuable to have these kinds of sessions earlier during the day, when our productivity is higher."

"It was a good idea to prepare in advance for this session as that is what made it efficient. It is great to see that the work package 4 will be shaped by our work without having to produce material that is outside of our expertise, so we can efficiently incorporate it in our research development."

However, one ESR reacted more negatively:

"It's still a bit unclear to me how this is going to help. There was also not enough time to provide the information requested by the leaders of each group, which resulted in several of the projects being misrepresented or misunderstood."

Day 3 consisted of four sessions. First was "Innovations in housing research: What next?", positively received by the ESRs, and one of the few sessions rated higher by the ESRs than the supervisors:

"Both presenters gave very insightful presentations for our research, especially looking at their methodological approaches that can be transferred to other contexts too."

"Roland's prisons' design focused on the well-being and environmental psychology evidence was a really interesting lecture. It is always fascinating to see the application of academic concepts and methodologies implemented in practice."

Though one supervisor commented:

"Online contribution was way too long."

Next was "RE-DWELL Assessment Framework". It was noted as an interesting session, but drew several suggestions:

"It was a useful session, I was just wondering if that could have been better organised by the three leaders giving Re-Dwell's context through state-of-the-art presentations on the three areas before/instead of presenting our research questions. Also some more context on what is a framework according to the so far research would be helpful."

"The similarities between the various PhD topics are becoming far clearer - it would be interesting to see where the tensions / contradictions were?"

"Interesting examples, more theoretical input on "social innovation" would have been useful to support the argument."

Next was the "Game session", which drew many positive comments by both ESRs and supervisors:

"The kick-off of the game with its positive and negative points was one of the most transdisciplinary moments of our network."

"I think the first trial of the serious game was a total success."

"The 'Game Session' was an engaging and interactive experience that provided a unique approach to engage with the framework. The session effectively combined education and entertainment, allowing participants to learn through gameplay."

"Excellent case of innovation in teaching."

Those who commented positively also had some suggestions for improvement:

"I would suggest instead of a second round, leave some more time for the first and a feedback session right after so that people's questions/doubts on the game are resolved."

"I personally enjoyed more the first round than the second one, as the whole team was slightly more tired, and collaboration and innovation were not carried out with the same enthusiasm as in the first one. A small break or a team swap would have improved this. As mentioned in Reading, some of the cards were difficult to understand, so it is necessary to have an expert on each of the fields on the table in order to play the game to its fullest."

One ESR reacted more negatively:

"Not suitable to be played online. Don't understand why we're playing a game if we're short on time and the deliverables are running late."

This was followed by "Station Hill Reading Development Site Tour". This was the lowest rated of the sessions, (overall average score of 3.6). While many mentioned the visit was well organised, one ESR questioned the suitability of the case study:

"I didn't understand the lessons to be learned from this site visit. For me it was very obvious that these type of speculative developments - where not even the mandatory affordable housing is allocated on site - is what in Re-dwell we are trying to confront through a transdisciplinary framework. I think that we are constantly seeing these types of developments on our cities, on media and on our previous working environments, so I would suggest that the Site tours on Re-dwell are more focused on innovative practices that approach affordability and sustainability of housing in some way."

Day 4 included two sessions. First was "Regeneration projects: a microcosm of social housing activity" and drew positive comments:

"Amazing hospitality and insight by Clarion, and truly heartfelt by Elanor to offer a follow up session to complete the presentation on social value."

"The...session was enlightening and provided valuable insights into the dynamics and complexities of regeneration projects in the context of social housing."

This was followed by "Introduction to social value housing tool KTP (Knowledge Transfer Partnership)" session, which was also among the highest rated sessions among both ESRs and supervisors (4.5 overall average):

"Inspiring model of architecture practice and how they integrate aspects of sustainable design from the very early stages."

"Tom was a very honest and modest presenter and a very welcoming host at their amazing space."

Day 5 included two sessions. First, "WP4 discussion and outputs". This was the second lowest rated among the sessions (3.7 average among ESRs). There were many comments about the planning and limited timeframe of the session:

"The time and effort spent in preparation of the presentations on top of other workload that all of us had was not respected on this session. It was a good decision to condense the presentations of the 2nd and 3rd groups but not a good planning in the first place-

especially on our last activity in which we have learnt so much from past experiences. It was also unfair that there were ESRs that spent 20'+Q&A time without being interrupted and some that were asked to change their presentation course at the last moment and cut it in half without allowing time for any feedback or questions."

"I have a comment regarding the ESR presentations, which has more to do with the ESRs themselves rather than the organisation: very few people kept the 10' slot in the beginning, with some ESRs reaching close to 30' of slides, resulting in some of those presenting later on to have to run through their presentation, ending up sharing virtually nothing."

"I think the session should have been planned with a slightly more generous timeframe. It would have been great to have a bidirectional discussion in which we are talking about the development, outputs and findings in our research, but hear some feedback and comments from the supervisors that may be more connected/interested on our topics (other than our main supervisor). I find that these workshops and summer schools give us the opportunity to share knowledge with the outstanding academics that form the Re-dwell consortium, and it would be better if the ERS's could take greater advantage of that pool of knowledge in these events."

And the session "Wrap-up, conclusions and follow-up", which was very highly rated:

"The last session was very constructive and felt very much like an open discussion in which everyone was able to share their opinions."

"This session wrapped-up the summer school in a very positive note. Gathering around a table in an informal way allowed a relaxed collaboration and improvised pin-up of ideas to improve the Serious Game, to transfer it into the Re-Dwell framework and ultimately to compose the Handbook. Having around a table people."

Though one noted:

"It could have been more structured."

At the end of the survey respondents had the chance to offer any other suggestions. Many of the suggestions centred around teamwork, discussion, and collaborative working, especially from a transdisciplinary perspective:

"I have observed that smaller groups of 5/6 people where all the disciplines are represented and there is a mix of personalities and roles, are the ones that create more fruitful discussions. Taking this into consideration when creating the teams to develop a certain activity would be my only recommendation."

"The speakers were very interesting, although their selection was a bit more interesting for architects. I wish there was a local authority representative, either Reading or London, just to give some insights into social housing allocation procedures."

"I would suggest to replace preparatory task ahead of the activities -which also add a layer of stress, with hands on collaborative work."

"Less presentations and more workshop-based activities."

"At joint events, it is very important to work together and put less emphasis on presentations."

Others reflected on how the workshop related to the larger aims and outputs of the project:

"Time for coordination between partners for the production of the project deliverables is essential at this point. Some meetings were organized ad hoc in parallel to ESRs workshops. They are still necessary in the future and should involve more participants besides the WP leaders."

"My overall suggestion relates more to the final output of RE-DWELL, which I think should be the game itself, and maybe the report/framework would have a complementary role. I think if we are to propose something innovative, we should really turn our focus towards producing a game that is flexible and adaptable to different contexts, which employs the right language and the correct set of rules to ensure inclusion as much as possible. If we claim to be transdisciplinary, yet exclude the general public from our final output through a rigid report/framework full of academic jargon, wouldn't our raison d' être as a consortium automatically evaporate?"

One ESR noted a more negative reaction:

"I was asked to prepare several documents that were not used [...] I find the tasks unfit for purpose. The mismanagement of tasks and deliverables is unprofessional. Ultimately, the task distribution is disrespectful of my schedule. I hope the management team takes better care of setting tasks and deadlines going forward."

Overall, though, the sessions were noted with consistent positive tone and high ratings:

"I think Reading demonstrated how productive these meetings can be, so let's learn from that when organising the next activity in Delft."

Annex 1 – Event evaluation form

RE-DWELL Reading Summer School – Quality assessment

3 - 7 July, 2023

This evaluation is to be completed by all participants, ESRs as well as supervisors, co-supervisors, secondment representatives.

Your answers will help to improve the next network activities. Thanks for your cooperation!

1. Please select your profile

- a) ESR
- b) Supervisor
- c) Co-supervisor
- d) Secondment

2. How did you attend?

- a) Online
- b) Onsite
- c) Both

3. How would you rate the organization of the summer school? (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

4. Day 1 - Monday 3. Please evaluate "Knowledge and evidence-based housing: Creating impact in housing research" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

5. Day 1 - Monday 3. Briefly explain the reasons of "Knowledge and evidence-based housing: Creating impact in housing research" session evaluation

Open answer

6. Day 1 - Monday 3. Please evaluate "Tools and methods of POE" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

7. Day 1 - Monday 3. Briefly explain the reasons of "Tools and methods of POE" session evaluation

Open answer

8. Day 1 - Monday 3. Please evaluate "Workshop - Reflect on Assignments" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

9. Day 1 - Monday 3. Briefly explain the reasons of "Workshop - Reflect on Assignments" session evaluation

Open answer

10. Day 2 - Tuesday 4. Please evaluate "Innovation in finance models for affordable housing: CLTs and Co-housing" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

11. Day 2 - Tuesday 4. Briefly explain the reasons of "Innovation in finance models for affordable housing: CLTs and Co-housing" session evaluation

Open answer

12. Day 2 - Tuesday 4. Please evaluate "Innovation in housing design" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

13. Day 2 - Tuesday 4. Briefly explain the reasons of "Innovation in housing design" session evaluation

Open answer

14. Day 2 - Tuesday 4. Please evaluate "Discussion New models of affordable housing" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

15. Day 2 - Tuesday 4. Briefly explain the reasons of "Discussion New models of affordable housing" session evaluation

Open answer

16. Day 2 - Tuesday 4. Please evaluate "RMT3 course: Exploring gaps and challenges in the transfer of research results" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

17. Day 2 - Tuesday 4. Briefly explain the reasons of "RMT3 course: Exploring gaps and challenges in the transfer of research results" session evaluation

Open answer

18. Day 2 - Tuesday 4. Please evaluate "Work package 4" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

19. Day 2 - Tuesday 4. Briefly explain the reasons of "Work package 4" session evaluation

Open answer

20. Day 3 - Wednesday 5. Please evaluate "Innovation in housing research: What next?" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

21. Day 3 - Wednesday 5. Briefly explain the reasons of "Innovation in housing research: What next?" session evaluation

Open answer

22. Day 3 - Wednesday 5. Please evaluate "RE-DWELL Assessment Framework" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

23. Day 3 - Wednesday 5. Briefly explain the reasons of "RE-DWELL Assessment Framework" session evaluation

Open answer

24. Day 3 - Wednesday 5. Please evaluate "Game session" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

25. Day 3 - Wednesday 5. Briefly explain the reasons of "Game session" session evaluation

Open answer

26. Day 3 - Wednesday 5. Please evaluate "Station Hill Reading Development Site Tour" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

27. Day 3 - Wednesday 5. Briefly explain the reasons of "Station Hill Reading Development Site Tour" session evaluation

Open answer

28. Day 4 - Thursday 6. Please evaluate "Regeneration projects: a microcosm of social housing activity" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

29. Day 4 - Thursday 6. Briefly explain the reasons of "Regeneration projects: a microcosm of social housing activity" session evaluation

Open answer

30. Day 4 - Thursday 6. Please evaluate "Introduction to social value housing tool KTP (Knowledge Transfer Partnership)" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

31. Day 4 - Thursday 6. Briefly explain the reasons of "Introduction to social value housing tool KTP (Knowledge Transfer Partnership)" session evaluation

Open answer

32. Day 5 - Friday 7. Please evaluate "WP4 discussion and outputs" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

33. Day 5 - Friday 7. Briefly explain the reasons of "WP4 discussion and outputs" session evaluation

Open answer

34. Day 5 - Friday 7. Please evaluate "Wrap-up, conclusions and follow-up" session (from 1-lowest to 5-highest)

- a) 1
- b) 2
- c) 3
- d) 4
- e) 5

35. Day 5 - Friday 7. Briefly explain the reasons of "Wrap-up, conclusions and follow-up" session evaluation

Open answer

36. Any other comments or suggestions for upcoming network activities (workshops, summer schools)

Open answer